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The De-dollarization of China-Related Financial and Economic Systems: Precursors Movements via Aligned Economic Blocs

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Abstract

This paper examines how de-dollarization is configured from a perspective of monetary diversifications, being an action of mutual interest between emergent economies that are part of the economic arrangements that China comprises. Currently, China's trade and political processes are characterized by their own aspects due to their differences from the usual system of unilateralism and monopoly, which is based on the predatory capitalism of the central states. It is in China's interest to project itself as a country based on an idea of commercial strength, monetary diversification, and weakening of the dollar through new economic arrangements. Within the process of contesting the dominant financial system, as historically identified since the 19th century, there has not been such a proactive participation of emergent states in aligning to change the status quo. Thus, relating new perspectives for analyzing the transformations of the international system. The paper's findings reveal that the process of greater integration of peripheral economies, based on mutual cooperation institutions, is essential in structuring strategies that mitigate dependence on the dollar in the international economic and financial system. The paper proposes that China's international trade policy is not limited to the role of BRICS Plus or the Belt and Road Initiative, but using a varied system of economic partnerships, formed by emergent economies, with such blocs integrated and centralized in China to create a more diversified financial environment for currencies.

Keywords: De-dollarization, Belt and Road Initiative, Monetary Diversification, BRICS Plus, Global South

1. The institutionalization of Chinese interstate relations: the Belt and Road Initiative and BRICS as a reflection of China's political and monetary interests

After the 2008 crisis, China, in addition to being politically strengthened, positioned itself as an economic power that was not submissive to Western economic demands, based on its autonomy in the face of international crises. The occurrence of the recent financial crisis stimulated the creation of new institutional arrangements, focusing on the emergence of new ones in the Global South (Grabel, 2013, p.5). In line with China's future objectives, in

2011, the admission of South Africa into BRIC, forming BRICS, meant the expansion of the relations that these emerging economies would have with each other given their strategic positions on their respective continents. Furthermore, just two years later, a new fiscal package for intercontinental economic boosting was announced by China, with the aim of promoting assertive trade strategies with internal and external impacts. Initially named *One Belt, One Road*, the initiative has come to be known as the New Silk Road due to its interconnected commercial aspect between Southeast Asia, the Middle East, Europe, and North Africa.

According to Cox (1996, p. 114), the long-term trend of the international order would be the replacement of the US global dominance, with one possibility being the structuring around groups of states, such as the EU in Europe and China and Japan in East Asia. However, Chinese cooperation with different states across the globe does not fit Cox's premise about the replacement of global dominance, as China highlights a homogeneous strengthening of the participating countries. Based on this aspect, it is observed that BRICS and the New Silk Road are not integrated within a dynamic of American participation, because, in addition to being connected economic arrangements, China intends them to be turning points in the status quo. In other words, the inclusion of the emerging peripheral economies of Latin America, Africa, the Middle East, and Europe within joint projects demonstrates a new political and economic organization in the system.

The short time between Chinese moves to develop prominent interstate relationships, especially post-crisis, should not be analyzed as a modest action. As evidenced by Jabbour and Paula, from the international financial instabilities, China demonstrated both control of the financial and industrial spheres and a high level of "socialization of investments"¹ due to new and better forms of economic planning had been constructed (2020b, p. 2). It is observed that the RMB internationalization strategies are intertwined in an even more ambitious perspective for China, seen as a process of detachment from the political, economic, and monetary traditionalism of the international system, which will be better elaborated later on regarding "de-dollarization."

According to Grabel, "recent crises have motivated policymakers to establish entirely new sub-regional, regional and transregional institutions; to build out existing institutions, substantially increasing their funding and capacity" (2019, p. 49). However, not only have financial crises driven the formation of regional organizations, but fiscal dependence, high interest rates, and unfavorable mandatory counterparties have contributed to this scenario of dissatisfaction because of the inequities of cooperation with Western States. Thus, China responds with collaborative proposals of mutual benefits to emergent countries, in addition to providing high availability of credit that would not normally be offered by traditional financial institutions, such as the IMF and the World Bank.

In the same year that the *New Silk Road* was announced, Xi Jinping declared the creation of the Asian Infrastructure Investment Bank (AIIB), an initiative integrated with the networks of Chinese development banks in financing capital for infrastructure in Asia (Pinto, 2021, p. 210). Furthermore, the AIIB would be one of the few multilateral organizations outside the US authority or its allies because the AIIB is composed of the China-Africa Development Fund, the China Development Bank, the African Development Bank Group, the New Development Bank (NDB)², and the Silk Road Fund (Vadell & Ramos, 2015).

In 2014, the New Silk Road Fund was set to have a total of US\$40 billion, with the aim of investing in medium to long-term projects. Nevertheless, Xi Jinping declared that there was the possibility of using resources from the AIIB, the NDB and the World Bank (Figueiredo, 2019). In effect, the coalition between the New Silk Road project and the AIIB reverberates as pillars within the process of financial assistance for regional infrastructure projects, resulting in greater Asian financial integration with the other participating States, not exclusive to emerging countries (Pinto, 2021, p. 211). The AIIB became a counterpoint in the international financial system, as reforms in the IMF, World Bank, and Asian Development Bank (ADB)³ were requested by States with lower purchasing power and, consequently, did not receive enough attention to their demands (Pinto, 2021, p. 211).

¹ Concept also used by Keynes in the book "The General Theory of Employment, Interest, and Money".

² The New Development Bank refers to the BRICS Bank, which was agreed at the 5th BRICS Summit in 2013 and was only founded in 2015.

³ The ADB would be an extension of Japanese interests in the Yen in Asia because the ADB is an institution highly influenced by the US to control the financial system in Asia (Pinto, 2021, p. 211).

Due to the New Silk Road, the trend of Asian deposits and bonds in RMB has grown exponentially as a result of the strong flow of capital within Asian countries, as a consequence of the initiative (Pinto, 2021, p. 212). Hence, in 2016, the RMB was officially integrated as part of the IMF's unit of account, in the Special Drawing Right (SDR) basket, which is the same basket that other international reference currencies are also included, such as the Dollar, the Euro, the British Pound Sterling, and the Yen (France Presse, 2016). According to Prasad (2016, p. 85), there has been a significant increase in the indicators of RMB use within international monetary transactions, even though it is at a low level, but it is prominent in the main foreign exchange markets. "In any case, the allocation of the RMB into the SDR basket does not aim to increase demand for it by central banks in the short term, but rather to incorporate this currency into the international system and encourage further financial reforms in China" (Martins, 2018, p. 14, translated by the author).

Through Cox's analysis (1981, p. 237), it is understood that the projection of a new hegemony is based on the social structure of power that is generated in the internationalization of production. In this regard, the consolidation of a new hegemonic State is defined by the international dominance of capital in alignment with the main economies, in addition to the perpetuation of the State through its internationalization (Cox, 1981, p. 237). However, the Chinese scope of transnational projects goes beyond the rapprochement with central economies because China uses strategies to form multilateral links with emerging peripheral economies to build more effective trade routes, obtain raw materials, and consumer markets.

According to the author (Cox, 1981, p. 237), an implicit process of continuity of monetarism as an orthodox economic policy would be necessary, in which the new hegemonic State would promote international economic stability (inflationary and exchange rate stability) through its own domestic political and social demands. Nonetheless, China not only does not fit into a policy of perpetuating monetarism and orthodoxy but positions itself with an international economic dynamic of mutual benefit between States through economic organizations. This is one of the consequences of the greater economic stability of States that are commercially close to China. Therefore, the New Silk Road, BRICS, and the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN), among other international organizations and projects, develop a type of Chinese centrality in their economic and financial arrangements because China is a point of economic stability, also due to its uninterrupted growth for more than three decades.

As evidenced in the Fortaleza Declaration, at the sixth BRICS meeting in 2014, "international governance structures designed within a different power configuration show increasingly evident signs of losing legitimacy and effectiveness, as transitional and ad hoc arrangements become increasingly prevalent, often at the expense of multilateralism" (United Nations, 2014). Furthermore, according to Batista Jr. (2016, p. 180) — former vice president of the NDB — BRICS is an "anti-hegemonic" agent based on its "multipolarization" character of the international economic and financial architecture. In other words, it is observed that the position of BRICS within the current international system is classified as a competitor to pre-established precepts because it is a new path for national development based on multilateralism among developing economies.

The financial nature of BRICS is reflected in its Reserve Fund and the use of the NDB to combat financial vulnerabilities and the shortage of financing for projects and sustainable infrastructure of its members due to some countries having a deficiency in the availability of credit within the hegemonic global financial architecture (Gabel, 2019, p. 63). In 2016, the initial projects were agreed with a total of US\$1,544 million in new operations, with China and India as the largest recipients of projects financed by the NDB, having added together accounted for 49% of the projects agreed (Costa, 2023, p. 32). The AIIB's alignment with the NDB for financing the New Silk Road is based on the combination of 13 regional and bilateral funds, which are accelerating China's financial development of energy and infrastructure (Gallagher, Kamal & Wang, 2016, p. 1). Thus, in the data relating to the annual growth of fixed-asset investment growth in China, it can be seen that, in mid-2016, there rose to 23,5% of state-owned fixed-asset investment growth, at the same time that private fixed-asset investment growth in China declined by 2,8% (Ross, 2016).

Although the AIIB represented the largest Chinese contribution to the evolving institutional landscape, China and the Bretton Woods institutions officials see these actions as complementary to the interests of Western multilateral

development banks, while the decisions of the US and Japan suggest an opposite view (Grabel, 2019, p. 65). As identified by Grabel (2019, p. 66-67), the foreign policies of European states and the US are promoting the dismantling of multilateral institutions, resulting in a power vacuum in the leadership of international multilateralism, which is being supported by the US due to the constant global economic instability. Consequently, according to Ocampo and Ortega (2022, p. 241-242), in the last two decades, the relationship between national development banks and multilateral development banks has provided an increase in long-term committed venture capital for innovation projects. However, in addition to the banks being more pragmatic after the 2008 crisis, private investors are also joining national development banks in venture capital funds.

US resistance against the China-led multilateralism is based on China's projection within the international economic system itself. "It would be extremely naive not to realize that China, in its pursuit of rapid economic growth, does not take advantage of gaps in the international geopolitical movement to further its own interests" (Jabbour, 2006, p. 52). In this sense, China's political strength has developed through its approximation with peripheral economies, which were historically invisible to central countries, with China's relations with emerging peripheral economies being one of the points of contention for international hegemony (Jabbour, 2012, p. 285).

As illustrated in the Fig. 1, the New Silk Road was designed to be divided into 6 economic corridors, which would mostly pass through more peripheral economies than central economies, separated into:

- 1) New Eurasia Land Bridge; 2) China-Mongolia-Russia; 3) China-Central Asia-West Asia (it will pass through the Middle West); 4) China-Indochina Peninsula; 5) China-Pakistan; and 6) Bangladesh-China-India-Myanmar economic corridor (Carletti, Ana, *apud* Pinto, 2021, p. 228).

The initiative is designed to go beyond the construction of high-tech logistics mechanisms because, through the Chinese alliance with at least 71 representative countries — in 2018 —, China promotes economic partnerships that account for 60% of the world's population and $\frac{1}{3}$ of international trade (The World Bank, 2018).

Figure 1: New Silk Road's corridors

Source: Sarker, Md Nazirul Islam & Hossin, Md & Yin, Xiaohua & Sarkar, Md., 2018.

It is essential to emphasize the growing dependence of US and European companies on Chinese productive, logistical, and economic advantages (Jabbour, 2012, p. 285). For example, in 2012, 40% of Chinese exports to the US were from US companies located in Chinese territory (Jabbour, 2012, p. 270). China's internal production chains not only integrated China with the international market but also consolidated the country as a major investor

in advanced logistics projects, which differentiates China from other states by having the technical development that prevents foreign companies from returning to their countries of origin (Jabbour & Gabriele, 2021, p. 239). With this in mind, US sanctions against Chinese industrialization would backfire on its own economic structure. As an illustration of the economic power of the New Silk Road, according to the Ministry of Commerce of the People's Republic of China (2019), trade between countries participating in the initiative grew 16.3% from 2017 to 2018, establishing a total volume of commercial transactions at the level of US\$1.3 trillion.

The institutionalization process permeates a particular stabilizing and perpetuating order, with state institutions and arrangements as a reflection of the prevailing power of the member states, which delimit a collective image of possible opposition to existing trends (Cox, 1981, p. 291). More simply, the Chinese position of organizing new economic arrangements favorable to emerging states, from blocs to interregional and continental initiatives, contributes to the perspective of divergence from the current economic structure centered on the USA.

This is because the economic and financial reforms embraced by China are characterized as new waves of institutional innovations due to the fact that, in summary, the growth of the private sector in a quantitative manner, while the public sector grows qualitatively (Jabbour & Gabriele, 2021, p. 253). Thus, it is analyzed that the Chinese economic projection is closely connected with the country's monetary interests, because, according to the "13th Five-Year Plan for National Economic and Social Development of the People's Republic of China" of 2016, there is a state interest in promoting the internationalization of the RMB through greater flexibility and convertibility of the capital account of its balance of payments, which will be aided by the internationalization of Chinese financial institutions (National Development and Reform Commission People's Republic of China).

2. De-dollarization: BRICS as a institutional tools for emerging economies

Although China intends to reduce its dependence on the dollar, there is still a strong Chinese demand for it, as in 2018 China held around US\$4 trillion in its monetary reserves — with an estimated 70% to 80% of this invested in dollar-denominated assets (Martins, 2018, p. 14). In Chart 1, China drastically increased its international reserves throughout the 2000s, establishing a certain stability from 2016 onwards. In this regard, the fall in the value attributed to the dollar would not only affect the international economy, but would also lead to the devaluation of China's own reserves because, in 2018, China also stood out for holding 18,7% of the total public debt securities of the United States, as shown in Table 1.

Chart 1: China's accumulation of international reserves (US\$ million)

Source: Author's estimates based on The World Bank data, 2024.

Table 1: List of largest creditors of US government debt securities

Country	January 2018	Debt percentage
China	US\$1,16 trillion	18,70%
Japan	US\$1,00 trillion	17,00%
Ireland	US\$327,50 billion	5,20%
Brazil	US\$265,70 billion	4,20%
Switzerland	US\$251,10 billion	4,00%
United Kingdom	US\$243,30 billion	3,90%
Cayman Islands	US\$241,90 billion	3,90%
Luxembourg	US\$220,90 billion	3,50%

Source: Author's estimates based on Forbes data, 2018.

However, the strengthening of Chinese trade dynamics is not limited to the growing surplus alone, as it relies on an increase in South-South monetary and financial relations, as a strategy for de-dollarizing the system. According to Kuehnlenz, Orsi, and Kaltenbrunner (2023, p. 2), BRICS countries, mainly China and Russia, are in the process of composing an international financial structure that is neither ordered by the dollar, nor US-centered institutions (as well as the IMF and the World Bank) nor adhered to the SWIFT⁴ (Society for Worldwide Interbank Financial Telecommunication) system. Cooperation for the development of new mechanisms to reduce dependence on the dollar is expanded among emerging peripheral economies, such as the use of “regional monetarism” (Fritz, Kaltenbrunner, Mühlich, & Orsi, 2023, p. 819). Therefore, since the creation of the Cross-Border Interbank Payments System (CIPS) in 2015, China has been developing measures to reduce intra-regional financial asymmetries through systems integrated with the RMB, although CIPS still has negligible relevance in the international financial system if compared to SWIFT. Based on CIPS statistics, by the end of 2020, the banking system already covered 99 countries and regions, in which all ASEAN countries have joined and another 876 direct and indirect participants from Asia (Gao, 2023, p. 239).

As highlighted in the last topic, the internalization of the RMB is deferred within a framework linked to the economic arrangements that Chan has developed, such as the New Silk Road and BRICS, with the growth in the use of the Chinese currency being a consequence of these achievements. Li (2019, p. 57) analyzed that, although the Central Bank of China uses forms to achieve effective control of the RMB through the statutory reserve ratio, open market business, and discount policy, there is still the possibility of loss of control of the macroeconomic regulation of domestic monetary policy. In this sense, China strategically stipulates that its trade relations will be fixed in the RMB due to the positions of these Chinese monetary activities centralized in key sectors. For example, the fixing of Saudi Arabia's⁵ Oil sales in RMB resulted in greater access for China to energy resources through the use of the so-called “petroyuan” (Leal, 2023, p. 18). The Year-on-Year Report of the Central Bank of China, published in 2020, described that cross-border payments and receipts in RMB for commodity trade (crude oil, iron ore, and others) totaled 252.57 billion yuan, representing an increase of 16,4% year-on-year (The People's Bank of China, 2021, p. 17).

Although in 2020, the expansion of cross-border portfolio investment settled in RMB totaled 16.50 trillion yuan, which represents a 73.6% year-on year growth (The People's Bank of China, 2021, p. 15), China's use of the US bonds and stocks as an economic resource remains present. In 2022, China sold approximately US\$173.2 billion (17%) of US bonds, as a result of the FED's interest rate hike, but mainly as a result of US political and economic

⁴ The SWIFT system is a major mechanism for communicating international financial, and banking transactions between private and public institutions, and has been influenced by the G10 countries (Germany, Belgium, Canada, the United States, France, Italy, Japan, the Netherlands, the United Kingdom, Sweden, and Switzerland) since its foundation.

⁵ “[...] Saudi Arabia, in addition to traditionally being a country aligned with the United States, has important US military bases on its territory. Its ability to exercise an independent and full foreign policy, especially on sensitive issues of international relations, such as monetary diplomacy linked to oil pricing, clashes directly with Washington's basic interests” (Metri, M., 2023, p. 424)

actions against Moscow. Since the beginning of 2022, the US has restricted Russia's access to its foreign reserves due to the Ukrainian War, generating an equally negative effect on China, due to its influence on Russian-owned bonds (Nikkei Asia, 2023). However, before the war, Russia previously created economic articulations with the aim of mitigating future sanctions from Western countries, expanding alternative payment mechanisms, such as the RMB and other currencies (Frankel, 2023, p. 8).

Furthermore, the movement towards de-dollarization of the global economic and financial system is separate from the perception of pure monetary diversity because protecting national economies from US-led economic sanctions is equally an unique objective within the reduction of the dollar's prominence. According to Sergey Glazyev, former Russian Minister of Foreign Economic Relations, the economic sanctions launched against Russia by the US, the European Union, and England were the imperative for accelerating the beginning of the dismantling of the dollar-based economic order (Janata Weekly, 2022). In Cox's view (1981, p. 231), the international economic structure was only delimited within a paradigm of US dominance, but also of the forced maintenance of power hierarchies, which are hidden in the development of negotiations between the parties. In this way, US financial sanctions consolidated the maintenance of the economic and financial order of the current system, but also corroborated the alliance of affected agents in partnerships with perspectives opposed to the status quo.

Table 2: Composition of U.S. Sanctions Programs

País	2021
Venezuela	5%
Russia	5%
Iraq	6%
Syria	7%
DPRK	9%
Iran	21%
Other	47%
-	Total of financial sanctions: 176

Source: Author's estimates based on U.S Department of the Treasury, 2021.

Table 2, in addition to addressing US financial sanctions, shows the division of antagonistic relations between the US and the countries listed. For example, Iran's leadership among countries financially sanctioned by the US is due to US pressure to disconnect SWIFT from Iranian banks (Zucker, 2021, p. 32). According to Frankel (2023, p. 7), the frequent increase in the use of sanctions by the US causes some countries to move away from allying with the dollar. Or, more pragmatically, it causes the search for alternatives. Consequently, it is analyzed that China develops commercial rapprochements with both US allies and its opponents. In a similar vein, it is understood that the fear of a dollar-led system is inherent to US allies and rivals because, due to the US sanctions against Iran, countries and companies with commercial relations with Iran have begun a process of searching for monetary alternatives for direct payments (Zucker, 2021, p. 33). Similarly, with the aim of generating greater monetary flexibility in the French financial system, China has begun to allow banks located in France to pay debts in Yuan through investments in China or through the purchase of imports (Kondratov, 2021, p. 43).

[...] Historically, to become hegemonic, a state would have to found and protect a world order which was universal in conception, i.e., not an order in which one state directly exploits others but an order which most other states (or at least those within reach of the hegemony) could find compatible with their interests. Such an order would hardly be conceived in inter-state terms alone, for this would likely bring to the fore oppositions of state interests (Cox, 1983, p. 171)

In parallel with the dollarized economic system, China uses the common interest of the other states in monetary diversification to consolidate strategic alliances with objectives that are opposed to the current financial and

economic structure. The aim would be similarly “non-exploitative,” as mentioned by Cox, because reducing the role of the dollar would bring greater economic freedom, essentially to peripheral economies. This process, although prone to reprisals by the hegemonic state, is promoted by China through economic advantages of mutual benefits between the parties. This is also because US economic sanctions are another condition for closer relations between peripheral countries and the Chinese economy — as identified in the previous topic. However, unlike how Cox wrote about the difficulty of interstate coalition, China develops an antagonism to the dollar as one of the central points of interstate interest for de-dollarization, reconciling favorable economic benefits of the Chinese economy with the increase in the country’s monetary independence.

China’s rapprochement with the BRICS member countries permeates the intention of monetary expansion. According to Putin, during a visit by Xi Jinping to Russia in March 2023: “We have reached 65% of the trade volume with settlements in our local currencies, and this will allow us to secure international trade from the influences of third countries and reduce our exposure to the currency market (Sky News, 2023)⁶.

Following the BRICS initiative to create a new international payment system, Enoch Godongwana, South Africa’s finance minister, states that the institution seeks to create trade facilities in local currencies, even though Russia is giving greater priority to using this system as an alternative to SWIFT (Reuters, 2023). Not only that, Naledi Pandor, South Africa’s minister of international relations and cooperation, reported that leaders from more than 23 countries⁷ have confirmed their interest in joining BRICS (TeleSUR, 2023).

India, in parallel, suffers more instability due to its links with Russian monetary diversification proposals, because, although in early 2023 there was a signal of trading Russian oil in Yuan between both countries, the increase in barrel prices imposed by the US pressured India not to include the Yuan as a payment currency (Bloomberg, 2023). In other words, to the extent that India’s economic relations with the US are more dependent, it is observed that the US articulation is not passively attributed within the actions opposing its currency in the current context, with the use of its monetary and economic influence being essential in the privileged maintenance position of the Dollar.

In agreement with what Dilma Rousseff, president of the NDB, stated in an interview with China’s international news channel, one of the current problems is the non-convertibility of the currencies of the Global South countries in foreign trade, with the position of the dollar as the international reference currency being an “exorbitant privilege”⁸ (CGTN, 2023). In the same month, Dilma Rousseff announced the NDB’s evaluation of issuing debts in Rand⁹, Real, and Rupees¹⁰ for loans, since there are already loans in RMB (Folha de S.Paulo, 2023).

Unlike the New Silk Road, where China is more planned to incorporate the RMB as an alternative currency, BRICS is being developed as an economic arrangement of mutual interests, in which de-dollarization is included. Consequently, since the announcement of Saudi Arabia and Iran’s entry into BRICS in August 2023, Chinese political articulations have established their strategic economic association through the duality of US foreign policy, which is reflected in their interstate relationships. This is because, as defined in Table 2, due to the fact that Iran has 21% of US financial sanctions, it becomes easier for the country to join the institution. Furthermore, the inclusion of Egypt, Ethiopia, the United Arab Emirates, and Argentina would be an expansion of BRICS in the African and Latin American continents, consolidating an increase, not only in national medium and long-term economic growth projects, but in sectors that are fundamental to maintaining economic development, such as the oil sector led by the three Middle Eastern countries. Therefore, BRICS is linked to financial pluralization, because, given the importance of the countries already present and the interest of other emergent economies in participating, de-dollarization is a friction for the US and its allies. In other words, as stated by French President Emmanuel

⁶ As analyzed by Sergey Glazyev in the same month, the debate on a new currency within the Shanghai Cooperation Organization, although surrounded by strong obstacles, is an important possibility for the development of the energy sector trade between China, Russia, India, and Iran, given that there is an increase in bilateral trade in their own currencies (The Candle.co, 2023).

⁷ The countries that applied to join BRICS were: Algeria, Argentina, Bangladesh, Bahrain, Belarus, Bolivia, Venezuela, Vietnam, Honduras, Egypt, Indonesia, Iran, Cuba, Kazakhstan, Kuwait, Nigeria, Palestine, Ethiopia, United Arab Emirates, Saudi Arabia, Senegal, and Thailand.

⁸ Dilma Rousseff made a clear reference to the book “Exorbitant Privilege: The Rise and Fall of the Dollar and the Future of the International Monetary System”, by Barry Eichengreen (2011), given the French dissatisfaction with the privileged position of the dollar in 1960.

⁹ Official currency of South Africa.

¹⁰ Official currency of India.

Macron, the expansion of BRICS is a “fragmentation of the world” (Sputnik, 2023), however, of the dollarized world.

3. Chinese de-dollarization strategies in the context of strengthening South-South relations and the war in Ukraine

Although Torres and Pose (2018, p. 18) argued that the process of expanding the RMB as a monetary alternative in the international system stagnated in 2018 due to the low convertibility of the currency during the period, it is observed that the Ukrainian War was one of the predominant factors for the resumption of the RMB growth in international trade transactions. Since 2019, China and Russia have already agreed on de-dollarizing movements within the mutual commercial and financial development of both countries, which were based on using their respective national currencies in bilateral financial transactions (Kondratov, 2021, p. 44). Thus, with the advancement of Western isolationist economic sanctions against Russia, it is understood that, in addition to favoring Russia’s rapprochement with emerging economies, they corroborated the Sino-Russian financial and economic coalition.

According to a document from the European Parliament (2022), the Ukrainian War resulted in the greatest financial instability in the price policy within the Eurozone, since, through the inflationary escalation in Europe, the significant deterioration of public trust in the European Central Bank. In contrast, Russia has seen positive economic growth even one year after the start of the war, given growth from -1.2% in 2022 to 3.59% in 2023 (O’Neill, 2024). This established Russia as a unique economic agent within the European economic and financial sphere. In this sense, Russia’s interstate relationship with emerging countries has incorporated an attraction into the de-dollarization policy developed between Russia and China since the mid-2000s (Kondratov, 2021), also due to Russia’s necessity to drain resources abroad — which were traded with Western Europe before the war.

In 2023, the debate about the creation of a new currency integrated into BRICS was intensified by the desire for monetary emancipation from the dollar that the member countries have. The development of closer relations between the member states began with the political-economic changes of the Ukrainian War, because, given the greater use of the RMB in commercial transactions between the participating states, an unofficial monetary diversification is observed. This is because, through the economic and financial sanctions imposed on Russia by Western countries since the beginning of the war, Russia’s trade relations with its partners have been strengthened, boosting imports from China and India, while there has been a drastic reduction in Russian imports from the European Union, Japan, England, and the USA, as illustrated in Chart 2. This process, in addition to being beneficial to China, establishes a favorable environment for the projection of the RMB and other currencies in the Russian financial system, since, according to Andrei Belousov, Deputy Prime Minister of Russia, by the end of 2023, bilateral trade between Russia and China was defined at 95% use in the Yuan and Ruble, with the Yuan currently being the primary foreign currency in Russia¹¹ (Chen, 2024).

¹¹ Prior to the economic sanctions on Russia, the country traded mainly in dollars or rubles (Chen, 2024).

Graph 2: Change in imports from Russia by country (2019-2023)

Source: Wu, Ashley, 2023, apud *The New York Times*, 2023.

As of 2024, the official integration of Saudi Arabia, the United Arab Emirates, Egypt, Iran, and Ethiopia into BRICS resulted in a more robust configuration for the economic arrangement, given the total representation of its members in global GDP at 36% and 50% of the planet's hydrocarbon reserves (Valor-São Paulo, 2024). However, while some countries declared interest in joining BRICS, Argentina refused to join the bloc, due to its position against the bloc, mainly in favor of the USA (Valor-São Paulo, 2024). As described by Cox (1981, p. 219), institutions can become a battleground of opposing tendencies, with Javier Milei's refusal being an illustration of permanence in the economic status quo of links to structures more focused on the North Global. As set out in the European Parliament (Jütten, Marc and Falkenberg, Dorothee, 2024), the European Union declared its fear of developing further trade relations with BRICS+ due to political differences in the conflicts in Ukraine and Gaza, but, essentially, due to the concern of the member of the Parliament's Committee on International Trade (INTA) about the expansion of BRICS+ and its potential currency and its consequence on the European Union's trade policy.

Authors such as Kuehnlenz et al. (2023) and Zharivok (2023) show that an alternative to de-dollarization would be the formulation of a digital currency. Although the authors discussed this before the entry of the new members of the economic arrangement, Zharivok (2023) analyzes that cryptocurrencies are an option for BRICS because they are not tied to a central monetary authority, but it is difficult to predict the scope of a new currency in view of international use. On the other hand, Kuehnlenz et. al. (2023) establish reasoning aimed at the foundation of a Central Bank of Digital Currencies, which would be more technologically advanced, since, the hybridization of virtual and physical currencies, monetary diversity would increase efficiency and reduce the costs of international transactions. In any case, it is analyzed that, through both authors, the construction of a less dollarized international economic and financial system must be designed through the distancing of the current financial structures, as well as SWIFT.

By launching the digital yuan pilot initiative, in which Russia is already involved, China is responding to the dollarized system based on the challenge of a new financial digital revolution by adopting their own state control over international monetary policy (Zharivok, 2023, p. 14). Russia's interest in de-dollarization is based on the protectionist prerogative of the national economy because there is an intention to avoid external actions of internal economic decline (Zharivok, 2023, p. 15). For example, Western economic sanctions affected the market value of the Ruble by 30%, even though Russia previously established payment alternatives in RMB or non-dollarized currencies (Frankel, 2023 p. 7). Therefore, the War in Ukraine demonstrated a more optimizing perspective for Russia in developing de-dollarizing alternatives — which are mostly supported by China —, but which also

encouraged the dynamization and grouping of States from the South Global interested in a financial and economic system of an emancipatory nature.

According to Cox (1981, p. 219), it is necessary to distinguish between hegemonic and non-hegemonic structures because hegemony cannot be reduced to a purely institutional dimension. In other words, reflecting what BRICS+ tends to be, the structuring of its situation is not limited to China's interests alone, but is organized through mutual interests among its members, given the commitment to integration and intra-institutional coalition for de-dollarization. Consequently, the movement towards greater South-South relations is a relatively new international order within the current international system, which remains aimed at perpetuating and privileging developed countries in interstate relations. Although BRICS+ remains with a reduced number of members compared to other more consolidated economic arrangements, China is strengthening its economic ties beyond the bloc, given the New Silk Road initiative as a pivot for developing more effective intercontinental integration.

In recent years, the expansion of South-South relations has shown that countries are positioning themselves to mitigate the harmful effects on their own economies. The de-dollarization of more emancipatory monetary purposes is being developed with the perspective of emerging countries to reduce their monetary dependence on the dollar, since, to the detriment of US objectives, the use of the "weaponization of the dollar," also called by Frankel (2019), is a reality in the current US strategy. According to the economist (2019), the applicability of the dollar as a weapon refers to the US exploitation of the currency's dominance in order to expand the extraterritorial reach of US law and policy. However, the implementation of the dollar's ordering position is contradicted within the Russian sphere, given that, in an interview with Tucker Swanson¹², Russian President Vladimir Putin discussed the US expectation of the collapse of the Russian economy after sanctions, but as a result of monetary diversification, the Russian economic and financial system remained relatively stable.

This event is not only due to Chinese collaboration in the monetary pluralization of Russian trade relations, but also due to the desires of China and other emerging peripheral economies to contain the influence of the dollar in the global economic and financial system. Unlike BRICS+, where there is a greater projection of mutual interests among member states, the New Silk Road is characterized as a non-institutional initiative with a logistical purpose, which would benefit China by expanding the reach of the RMB in international trade. In contrast to the analysis formulated by Cox (2007, p. 119-120) regarding the role of international organizations, China is building a structure of transcontinental magnitude that reduces the global domination of hegemonic powers, being a project to also reduce hierarchies between states given the protection of the New Silk Road against US interference.

China's intensified positioning in designing new alternatives for greater use of the RMB is a result of the very compulsory actions of the top of the hierarchy of the international and financial system, because, in order to avoid coercive movements against their economies, emerging states take advantage of Russian conduct to integrate into the new financial dynamics. With the fact that the Ukrainian War has forced Russia to take a more active stance in mitigating the negative effects of economic sanctions from the West, China has had economic advantages that have brought Russia closer to agreeing to economic measures that both favor monetary diversification and expansion of the RMB. The purpose of both being to expand de-dollarization in the system. Therefore, it is analyzed that the increasingly close alignment between China, Russia, and other countries of the South Global in the last two years is part of a ramifying Chinese strategy, which directs different interstate and institutional segments to promote de-dollarization.

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¹² kremlin. Interview to Tucker Carlson. Youtube, 9 February 2024. Available in: <<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hYfByTcY49k>>, 21/04/2024. Interview between Tucker Carlson and Vladimir Putin.

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